

COMPARISON OF NATIONAL BURDENS OF INCOMING MIGRANTS TO THE EUROPEAN UNION WITH FOCUS ON INTEGRATION ASPECTS

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Abstract: Migration of persons in the European Union is of interest to the professional, but especially after 2015 also to the lay public. Despite the high level of interest, the use of legal concepts as well as a general understanding of national burdens on incoming migrants seems insufficient. The authors therefore aim, also with regard to the legal bases of legal and irregular migration, to compare the situation of immigration in the European Union, especially in terms of migration waves since 2006, and to identify the countries most affected by the arrival of migrants. As the authors point out, one of the main challenges of the member states of European Union is the integration of migrants into their society.

Keywords: immigration, labor migration, integration, European Union

JEL: J61, K37, O15

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the migration of persons due to the emergence of the so-called 'migration crisis' in the European Union in 2015 has been the subject of discussions, debates, as well as political speeches. It is natural that the topic, by its complexity, "deserved" intensive attention from both the lay and professional public. The aim of our contribution is therefore to point out the current immigration to individual states of the European Union, also with regard to legal bases of legal and irregular migration, to compare the situation of immigration in the European Union, especially in terms of migration waves since 2006 and identify the countries most affected by migrants.

The migration crisis is characterized by a high number of irregular migrants arriving to the European Union. In this case, it is essential to clearly distinguish between legal and irregular migration, irregular migrants and those entitled to protection and assistance under the asylum law as well as international conventions and to clarify other aspects and contexts.

1. LEGAL OR IRREGULAR MIGRATION? REFUGEES OR LABOR MIGRANTS?

With regard to the subject matter of the paper, we believe that it is beneficial and necessary to address briefly the legal documents dealing with the issue of migration of persons, especially for the purpose of identifying frequently used and not distinguished terms. In terms of burden and integration, it is necessary to treat differently legal and irregular migrants, as well as refugees, asylum-seekers or labor migrants, who form the largest proportion of migrants among the countries of the European Union.

Perhaps the most commonly used and well-known differentiation of migration is the motivation of arrival, resp. emigration to another country (unless we are talking about national migration). In this case, it is possible to speak of forced and voluntary migration (push and pull factors). Push factors have a rather negative character, because migrants are forced to leave the country (e.g. persecution, riots in the form of war conflicts, political instability, or other social and economic inequalities). Pull factors motivate the migrant to go to the destination country (e.g. work, leaving for the family, better standard of living, the possibility of career growth, better education opportunities).

It should be emphasized that both irregular migrants, who often come to the European Union for economic reasons, and migrants who are entitled to protection and assistance, come to the European Union. The legal basis in this case is the so-called Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees from 1951, resp. called „The Geneva Convention“, which the Slovak Republic has undertaken to respect along with the other Member States of the European Union.

A refugee is a person covered by the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees. In addition to the definition of refugee and his rights, the Convention on the Status of Refugees also regulates his obligations. A refugee has a fear of being persecuted because of race, religion, nationality, political beliefs or membership of a particular political group. This document further defines the issue of nationality, while granting refugee status to a stateless person who is outside his / her state of residence. The condition in this case is that the person cannot or does not want to return there due to the aforementioned concerns.

The other conditions for granting asylum or subsidiary protection are regulated separately by each Member State in their national legal systems. In the Slovak Republic, it is the Asylum Act (Act no. 480/2002 Coll. on asylum and on amendments to certain acts, as amended).

The characteristics of irregular (or legal) migrants and illegal migration can be based on Regulation (EU) 2016/399 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on a Union Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code). The Schengen Borders Code in Article 5 (Article 6 in codified version) lays down the conditions for the admission of third-country

nationals. According to Article 5 of the Schengen Borders Code, third-country nationals must comply with, for example the following conditions:

- have a valid travel document or documents,
- have a valid visa,
- justify the purpose and conditions of the intended stay,
- have sufficient means of subsistence during their intended stay; and
- return,
- are not considered to be a threat to public policy or internal security.

Other aspects of the legal status of irregular persons, including refugees, are governed by Directive 2008/115 / EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals (hereinafter: "Return Directive"). According to Art. 6 par. 1. The Return Directive, Member States shall issue a return decision to any third-country national staying illegally on their territory, but without prejudice to the exceptions referred to in paragraphs 2 to 5. Member States may also at any time decide to grant a separate residence permit to an irregular migrant for reasons worthy of special consideration. In this case no return decision is issued.

Koser (2007) distinguishes between an economic migrant and a political migrant in his distribution of migrants, in the first case the reasons for migration are mainly economic, in the second case the migrants act on political grounds.

Other important documents adopted at international and European level covering the protection of migrants include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment and others.

Due to the limitations of the scope of the contribution, it is not possible to deal in detail with all legal documents governing the migration of persons at international and European level.

Irregular migration, unlike legal migration, is a negative phenomenon, so it is natural that there is a need to take effective measures to eliminate it. The issue of irregular migration is very often associated with organized crime, in particular human smuggling, human trafficking or illegal employment. However, given the limitations of the scope and subject matter of our contribution, we will mainly deal with legal migration and its integration aspects.

Irregular migration, unlike legal migration, is mostly taken as a negative phenomenon, so it is natural that there is a need to take effective measures to eliminate it. The issue of irregular migration is very often associated with organized crime, in particular human smuggling, human trafficking or illegal employment. In certain cases

it is possible to advocate the use of illegal routes, eg. the issue of irregular refugees where there are no legal options for escape.

Migration is a natural sociological phenomenon that does not necessarily represent negative events. According to Slovak Business Agency (2018), legal migration is defined as crossing the border of the country with a valid travel document, where appropriate valid visas and permits are required to enter the country.

On the contrary to the irregular migration, legal migration and thus mobility of persons can bring positive aspect, it can be a mutual means of social, cultural and economic growth for all the concerned parties; the migrant himself, the destination country and the country of origin.

In the second part we are focusing on the comparison of the incoming migrants to the European countries and comparing the burdens put on each country.

2. COMPARISON OF THE NUMBER OF INCOMING MIGRANTS TO THE MEMBER STATES OF EUROPEAN UNION

For this comparison, we worked with Eurostat data for years 2006-2017 with a focus on the long-term immigration in individual countries of the European Union. We divided the European Union countries into the groups according to their geographical location for better comparison and visualization of the comparison.

It is important to note that in immigration we have taken into account the nature of the European Union countries in terms of migrants, divided into destination countries and transit countries. We assume that the South of Europe, in particular during the last migration wave in 2015, was a transit zone, while the northernmost countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, France and the Nordic countries like Sweden were important destination countries for immigrants and we think that those countries also experienced the greatest burden on admitting migrants.¹

At the end of this part of the paper we will compare the burden of individual countries on the basis of available data and we will present the possibilities of solving this situation in terms of integration of migrants from the perspective of integration policies, namely through the social economy entities.

2.1 Immigration in the states of Southern Europe

We included into the group of countries of Southern Europe: Spain, Italy, Malta and Portugal. In this group we observe that of the countries that represent the gateway to Europe for migrants, mainly from African countries or the Middle East, Spain and Italy were the most affected by the influx of migrants. If we compare recent years, the migration crisis in 2015 did not occur in these countries at most in 2015, but only in 2017, in the case of Spain, where the number of migrants exceeded half a million -

¹ Note: In this analysis we abstract from the related topics such as the country of origin, the reason for emigration from the country of origin, or other.

532,132 migrants. The second country with an increasing number of migrants was Italy, where the culmination also occurred in 2017, when 343,440 migrants arrived to the country.

Table 1: Immigration in Southern countries of European Union

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Spain	840 844	958 266	599 075	392 962	360 705	371 331	304 053	280 772	305 454	342 114	414 746	532 132
Italy	279 714	527 123	534 712	442 940	458 856	385 793	350 772	307 454	277 631	280 078	300 823	343 440
Malta	3 889	5 292	6 043	6 161	4 275	5 465	8 256	10 897	14 454	16 936	17 051	21 676
Portugal	22 741	29 661	29 718	32 307	27 575	19 667	14 606	17 554	19 516	29 896	29 925	36 639
Σ	1 147 188	1 520 342	1 169 548	874 370	851 411	782 256	677 687	616 677	617 055	669 024	762 545	933 887

Source: Eurostat, 2019

In contrast to the political and social unrest in recent years, however, this number of migrants has not been historically the highest in the case of these countries. If we compare these countries from the available data during the last 10 years in Table 1, but also in Graph 1, we can speak about the migration wave from the perspective of this group of European Union countries between years 2006 and 2008. Spain with nearly a million long-term migrants, who came to the country in 2007 (958,266 migrants). Italy recorded the highest influx in 2008, when 534,712 migrants arrived. In comparison with the last years, we can talk about double number in 2006-2008. As far as Italy is concerned, it has been a constant burden over the last decade in terms of long-term immigration. From the point of view of all European Union countries, however, Italy is fourth in the number of migrant inflows. However, the real problems of the country also lie in the transit of migrants, as it is the most geographically accessible transit zone to Europe (f.e. Lampedusa Island).

Graph 1: Immigration in southern countries of European Union

Source: Eurostat, 2019

As far as the number of migrants is concerned, the inflow of migrants to Spain in 2006-2007 is comparable to the inflow of migrants to Germany in 2015. The other two countries, Portugal and Malta, experienced a similar low-burden long-term immigration trend.

2.2 Immigration in the states of West Europe

The group of Western European countries is the largest group in terms of geographical distribution and we included here countries: Belgium, Denmark, Germany, France, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Ireland and the United Kingdom.

From the perspective of recent years and the migration crisis in 2015, the most prominent was the situation in Germany, where 1,543,848 long-term migrants arrived this year. Also in 2016 and 2017, their numbers were high.

Table 2: Immigration in Western countries of European Union

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Belgium	137 699	146 409	:	:	135 281	147 377	129 477	120 078	123 158	146 626	123 702	126 703
Denmark	56 750	64 656	57 357	51 800	52 236	52 833	54 409	60 312	68 388	78 492	74 383	68 579
Germany	661 855	680 766	682 146	346 216	404 055	489 422	592 175	692 713	884 893	1 543 848	1 029 852	917 109
Ireland	139 434	122 415	82 592	50 604	52 339	57 292	61 324	65 539	73 519	80 792	85 185	78 499
France	301 544	293 980	296 608	296 970	307 111	319 816	327 431	338 752	340 383	364 221	378 115	369 964
Luxembourg	14 352	16 675	17 758	15 751	16 962	20 268	20 478	21 098	22 332	23 803	22 888	24 379
Netherlands	101 150	116 819	143 516	122 917	126 776	130 118	124 566	129 428	145 323	166 872	189 232	189 646
United Kingdom	529 008	526 714	590 242	566 514	590 950	566 044	498 040	526 046	631 991	631 452	588 993	644 209
Σ	1 941 792	1 968 434	1 870 219	1 450 772	1 685 710	1 783 170	1 807 900	1 953 966	2 289 987	3 036 106	2 492 350	2 419 088

Source: Eurostat, 2019

From the countries of Western Europe, the United Kingdom and France are also highly affected by long-term migration. In the United Kingdom, the highest number of long-term immigration was registered in 2017, of 644,209 migrants. As regards France, the number of long-term immigrants is continuously around 300,000 migrants per year (with a maximum of 378,115 in 2016).

The migration policy of the state and the economic development of the country are also important factors related to the number of immigrants to a given country. In 2015, it was the German market that was open to migrants, also in terms of labor needs.

Graph 2: Immigration in western countries of European Union

Source: Eurostat, 2019

In this group of countries, Luxembourg, Denmark and Ireland are the least burdened countries with long-term migration. About Belgium and the Netherlands, the Netherlands has a higher number of long-term immigrants than Belgium, but their number was considerably lower than in Germany or France.

2.3 Immigration in the states of Northern Europe

The Nordic EU group consisted of Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, Finland and Sweden. Most long-term migrants came to Sweden, 163,005 migrants in 2016.

Table 3: Immigration in Northern countries of European Union

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Estonia	2 234	3 741	3 671	3 884	2 810	3 709	2 639	4 109	3 904	15 413	14 822	17 616
Latvia	8 212	7 517	4 678	3 731	4 011	10 234	13 303	8 299	10 365	9 479	8 345	9 916
Lithuania	7 745	8 609	9 297	6 487	5 213	15 685	19 843	22 011	24 294	22 130	20 162	20 368
Finland	22 451	26 029	29 114	26 699	25 636	29 481	31 278	31 941	31 507	28 746	34 905	31 797
Sweden	95 750	99 485	101 171	102 280	98 801	96 467	103 059	115 845	126 966	134 240	163 005	144 489
Σ	136 392	145 381	147 931	143 081	136 471	155 576	170 122	182 205	197 036	210 008	241 239	224 186

Source: Eurostat, 2019

In the case of Estonia or Latvia, the number of migrants did not exceed 20,000 during the reporting period. Comparing Finland and Sweden, it is clear that the destination for long-term migrants of these Nordic countries is clearly Sweden.

Graph 3: Immigration in Northern countries of European Union

Source: Eurostat, 2019

2.4 Immigration in the states of V4 and Austria

The assumption for assessing the long-term immigration in the countries of Central Europe is that they are the countries outside the main migration routes and these countries are more kind of a transit countries.

When comparing the V4 countries (Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary) with Austria, we can see that the highest number of long-term migrants was recorded in Poland and rose rapidly in 2009, from 15,275 migrants in 2008 to 189,166 migrants in 2009. In the following years the trend in Poland increased only in 2013, most migrants came to the country in 2014, 222,275 long-term migrants.

Table 4: Immigration of V4 countries and Austria

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Czechia	68 183	104 445	108 267	75 620	48 317	27 114	34 337	30 124	29 897	29 602	64 083	51 847
Hungary	25 732	24 361	37 652	27 894	25 519	28 018	33 702	38 968	54 581	58 344	53 618	68 070
Austria	98 535	72 862	73 772	69 295	70 978	82 230	91 557	101 866	116 262	166 323	129 509	111 801
Poland	10 802	14 995	15 275	189 166	155 131	157 059	217 546	220 311	222 275	218 147	208 302	209 353
Slovakia	5 589	8 624	8 765	6 346	5 272	4 829	5 419	5 149	5 357	6 997	7 686	7 188
Σ	208 841	225 287	243 731	368 321	305 217	299 250	382 561	396 418	428 372	479 413	463 198	448 259

Source: Eurostat, 2019

The second country with the highest number of migrants in this group is Austria, which recorded the highest number of migrants in 2015 - 166,323 migrants.

Graph 4: Immigration of V4 countries

Source: Eurostat, 2019

The Czech Republic recorded the highest increase in long-term migrants in 2007-2008, in 2008 it was 108,267 migrants. In Hungary, the influx of migrants has increased by more than double over the last 10 years. Minimum - 24,361 migrants arrived in Hungary in 2007. The highest number of longer term migrants arrived in the country in 2017, 68,070 migrants.

The least affected by the influx of long-term migrants is Slovakia, where the highest numbers were recorded in 2008, namely 8,765 migrants. In recent years, their number is around 7,000.

2.5 Immigration in the states of South-East Europe

The group of South-East European countries consisted of countries: Bulgaria, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Romania and Slovenia. Most long-term migrants during the reporting period came to Romania, where peaking occurred in 2017, totally 177,435 migrants.

Table 5: Immigration in South-East countries of European Union

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Bulgaria		1 561	14 103	18 570	26 615	25 223	21 241	25 597
Greece	63 094	63 298	66 529	58 613	60 462	60 089	58 200	57 946	59 013	64 446	116 867	112 247
Croatia	14 978	14 622	16 883	13 213	8 846	8 534	8 959	10 378	10 638	11 706	13 985	15 553
Cyprus	13 077	19 328	21 060	22 581	20 206	23 037	17 476	13 149	9 212	15 183	17 391	21 306
Romania			138 929	135 844	149 885	147 685	167 266	153 646	136 035	132 795	137 455	177 435
Slovenia	20 016	29 193	30 693	30 296	15 416	14 083	15 022	13 871	13 846	15 420	16 623	18 808

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
	111	128	274	260	254	253	281	267	255	264	323	370
Σ	165	002	094	547	815	428	026	560	359	773	562	946

Source: Eurostat, 2019

In Greece, the number of migrants also nearly doubled during the period under review, in 2016 when 116,867 migrants arrived, compared to 2015 when 64,446 arrived. The lowest influx of migrants was in Croatia, Slovenia and Cyprus, where these numbers are around 20,000 migrants per year in recent years. Similarly, this number is relatively stable in Bulgaria, the maximum of 26,615 long-term migrants was in 2014.

Graph 5: Immigration in south-eastern countries of European Union

Source: Eurostat, 2019

2.6 Immigration to the European Union

If we would count the number of migrants to the European Union for all countries under review during the reporting period, we can say that together 44.705.257 migrants came to the European Union. Of course, this figure reflects only the total number for the reference years, but does not take into account the movement between countries – internal mobility of people. For example, the fact that one migrant who came to one country in one year could become an immigrant for another country in the next year.

This number is therefore only approximate, we assume that these migrants are kind of refugees, or migrants looking for better economic conditions and remain in individual countries for a longer period of time.

According to the Eurostat statistics, the highest number of migrants came to Germany during the period with a total number of 8,925,050 migrants, and the lowest number of migrants was observed in Slovakia with 77,221 migrants during the monitored period (from 2006-2017).

Among the others, countries like Spain, Italy and the United Kingdom may have real problems in receiving and integrating long-term migrants into the labor market. These countries also have recorded the highest numbers of long-term migrants throughout the reporting period.

Table 6: Immigration in the countries of European Union

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	SUM
Belgium	137 699	146 409	:	:	135 281	147 377	129 477	120 078	123 158	146 626	123 702	126 703	1 336 510
Bulgaria	:	1 561	:	:	:	:	14 103	18 570	26 615	25 223	21 241	25 597	132 910
Czechia	68 183	104 445	108 267	75 620	48 317	27 114	34 337	30 124	29 897	29 602	64 083	51 847	671 836
Denmark	56 750	64 656	57 357	51 800	52 236	52 833	54 409	60 312	68 388	78 492	74 383	68 579	740 195
Germany	661 855	680 766	682 146	346 216	404 055	489 422	592 175	692 713	884 893	1 543 848	1 029 852	917 109	8 925 050
Estonia	2 234	3 741	3 671	3 884	2 810	3 709	2 639	4 109	3 904	15 413	14 822	17 616	78 552
Ireland	139 434	122 415	82 592	50 604	52 339	57 292	61 324	65 539	73 519	80 792	85 185	78 499	949 534
Greece	63 094	63 298	66 529	58 613	60 462	60 089	58 200	57 946	59 013	64 446	116 867	112 247	840 804
Spain	840 844	958 266	599 075	392 962	360 705	371 331	304 053	280 772	305 454	342 114	414 746	532 132	5 702 454
France	301 544	293 980	296 608	296 970	307 111	319 816	327 431	338 752	340 383	364 221	378 115	369 964	3 934 895
Croatia	14 978	14 622	16 883	13 213	8 846	8 534	8 959	10 378	10 638	11 706	13 985	15 553	148 295
Italy	279 714	527 123	534 712	442 940	458 856	385 793	350 772	307 454	277 631	280 078	300 823	343 440	4 489 336
Cyprus	13 077	19 328	21 060	22 581	20 206	23 037	17 476	13 149	9 212	15 183	17 391	21 306	213 006
Latvia	8 212	7 517	4 678	3 731	4 011	10 234	13 303	8 299	10 365	9 479	8 345	9 916	98 090
Lithuania	7 745	8 609	9 297	6 487	5 213	15 685	19 843	22 011	24 294	22 130	20 162	20 368	181 844
Luxembourg	14 352	16 675	17 758	15 751	16 962	20 268	20 478	21 098	22 332	23 803	22 888	24 379	236 744
Hungary	25 732	24 361	37 652	27 894	25 519	28 018	33 702	38 968	54 581	58 344	53 618	68 070	476 459
Malta	3 889	5 292	6 043	6 161	4 275	5 465	8 256	10 897	14 454	16 936	17 051	21 676	120 395
Netherlands	101 150	116 819	143 516	122 917	126 776	130 118	124 566	129 428	145 323	166 872	189 232	189 646	1 686 363
Austria	98 535	72 862	73 772	69 295	70 978	82 230	91 557	101 866	116 262	166 323	129 509	111 801	1 184 990
Poland	10 802	14 995	15 275	189 166	155 131	157 059	217 546	220 311	222 275	218 147	208 302	209 353	1 838 362
Portugal	22 741	29 661	29 718	32 307	27 575	19 667	14 606	17 554	19 516	29 896	29 925	36 639	309 805
Romania	:	:	138 929	135 844	149 885	147 685	167 266	153 646	136 035	132 795	137 455	177 435	1 476 975
Slovenia	20 016	29 193	30 693	30 296	15 416	14 083	15 022	13 871	13 846	15 420	16 623	18 808	233 287
Slovakia	5 589	8 624	8 765	6 346	5 272	4 829	5 419	5 149	5 357	6 997	7 686	7 188	77 221
Finland	22 451	26 029	29 114	26 699	25 636	29 481	31 278	31 941	31 507	28 746	34 905	31 797	349 584
Sweden	95 750	99 485	101 171	102 280	98 801	96 467	103 059	115 845	126 966	134 240	163 005	144 489	1 381 558

TIME	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	SUM
United Kingdom	529 008	526 714	590 242	566 514	590 950	566 044	498 040	526 046	631 991	631 452	588 993	644 209	6 890 203
SUM	3 545 378	3 987 446	3 705 523	3 097 091	3 233 624	3 273 680	3 319 296	3 416 826	3 787 809	4 659 324	4 282 894	4 396 366	44 705 257

Source: Eurostat, 2016

We can observe that there are also countries that didn't have so high numbers of immigrants during monitored period like Slovakia, Estonia and Latvia. During 11 years they received up to 100,000 numbers of incoming migrants to the each country.

Graph 6: Immigration in the countries of European Union

Source: Eurostat, 2019

On the graph 6 we can see that through the monitored period the most affected by migration are these countries: Germany, Spain, Italy and United Kingdom. The topic of immigration has been often discussed as one of the main reasons for Brexit - United Kingdom leaving from the European Union.

In context, in 2015, 4.7 million people moved to EU countries. An estimation is that at least 2.8 million people have gone from any EU country to third countries. However, these overall figures do not represent migration flows to / from the EU as a whole, as they also include flows between individual EU countries. Of the 4.7 million immigrants who came to the EU in 2015, it is estimated that up to 2.4 million citizens were from third countries, ie. from non-EU countries (Slovak Business Agency, 2019).

In absolute terms, the largest number of foreigners living to the date 1 January 2016 in the EU Member States were in Germany (8.7 million), the United Kingdom (5.6 million), Italy (5 million), Spain (4.4 million) and France (4.4 million). Foreigners in the

five Member States together accounted for 76% of the total number of foreigners living in all EU Member States (Slovak Business Agency, 2019).

It should be pointed out that the issue of irregular migration needs to be specifically examined and approached. Given the fact that irregular migration is a negative phenomenon that individual Member States are trying to stop, it is difficult to talk about integration processes. On the contrary, irregular migrants are to be returned to the countries of origin under applicable European law, unless this is precluded by their entitlement to refugee status under the Geneva Convention. The highest influx of irregular migrants in the period under review by FRONTEX can be identified in 2015, when the so-called migration crisis outbreak. While Greece was the main accession country to the EU during this period, it is currently Italy and Spain. In all cases, however, these are mainly transit countries and, despite migrants' illegality of entry and residence, migrants are interested in traveling further, e.g. to Germany or Sweden (Vyrostko, 2018). An overview of the number of irregular migrants detected upon accession to the European Union can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Number of detected incoming irregular migrants to the EU

Irregular migration to the EU						
	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
All borders	107 365	282 933	1822 177	511 731	204 719	150 114

Source: Own customization according to: Frontex, 2017, p. 47 and Frontex 2019, p. 42.

3. HOW TO DEAL WITH THE MIGRATION BURDEN?

The question remains to what extent the European Union market and individual countries are able to provide opportunities for the integration of migrants, whether in the labor market or in social dimensions. As mentioned in the introduction, a distinction needs to be made between legal and irregular migration; in the case of detected irregular migration, a person can be provided with assistance to return to the country of origin. In the case of legal migration there are instruments of assistance in the area of work, housing, etc.

There are growing initiatives of social economy, mostly in the west European countries, where social economy becomes the space of help to those ones who are disadvantaged in some way or in need.

According the literature, the social economy is based on the principle of association, solidarity, subsidiarity, fairness and equality, and consequently social inclusion of those who are in any way of disadvantage (Korimová a kol., 2008). It represents a space for creating conditions for the involvement of marginal groups into the labor process (Pčolinská, 2013).

According to the European Economic and Social Committee 'Social economy enterprises as the driving force for the integration of migrants' from 2018, the European Economic and Social Committee considers it essential that the European institutions, together with Member State governments, promote coordinated policies to achieve greater clarity, sustainability and the ways in which people from third countries can enter and settle in Europe, become its citizens or have access to international protection. The Committee calls on the Commission to pay particular attention to migrants who may be at risk of social exclusion, such as sick people, people with mental health problems, people with disabilities or older people. Social economy enterprises create quality jobs in sectors with a high share of manual labor, especially with a high proportion of third-country workers. Social economy enterprises, therefore, have a key role to play in areas related to the four key aspects of the integration process of migrants: health and assistance; accommodation; training and education (in particular raising awareness of the rights and obligations arising from establishment in the European Union); work and active inclusion of migrants in the host society (European Economic and Social Committee, 2018).

The integration of foreigners (migrants) in the EU countries seems to be an issue requiring effective and rapid solutions. For this reason, it is understandable that the European Union states adopt national as well as regional and local policy documents governing the progress of integration activities.

We believe that actors at regional and local level play a key role in integration. In practice, migrants ultimately come into contact mainly with local actors. These may be municipal authorities, but also various intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations. Undoubtedly, the work environment plays an important role (if the alien has succeeded in employment).

A deeper analysis of the integration of migrants in individual Member States of the European Union is the subject of further research.

CONCLUSION

Migration is a natural sociological phenomenon that does not necessarily represent negative events; on the contrary, migration and thus mobility of persons can be a mutual means of social, cultural and economic growth for all the parties concerned, the migrant himself, the destination country and the country of origin.

In this case, it is essential to clearly distinguish between legal and irregular migration, irregular migrants and those entitled to protection and assistance under the asylum law as well as international conventions and to clarify other aspects and contexts, and we offer the comparison at the first part of this paper.

Both economic migrants and refugees are currently coming to the European Union, choosing both legal and illegal routes. If states, especially those more burdened by the number of migrants arriving, are interested in successful integration of migrants,

it is essential that, in addition to promoting legal migration and measures against irregular migration, they draw up policy documents on integration and implement these activities in practice. We believe that one of these activities is the promotion of social entrepreneurship and cooperation with regional and local actors. According to the EESC opinion (2018), "Social economy enterprises can play a decisive role in social and labor inclusion activities, as they activate the potential of migrants, who in most cases have decided to leave their country of origin for the purpose of seeking better living conditions and jobs".

With our comparison of the burden of migrants on individual states of European Union, we conclude that not all countries are burdened at the same level and with higher number of migrants, countries need to look for the ways of integration of the long-term migrants, especially those under the international protection. According the trend of the European institutions suggestions, we also see the one of the possibilities in the offer the integrational efforts through the subject of the social economy.

The article is written as the part of the projects VVGS-2019-1018 *Dynamics of the development of the social economics in Slovakia and its use in self-government* and VEGA 1/0367/17 *Economic, legislative and institutional preconditions and perspectives of social and solidarity economy in the V4 countries in relation to the promotion of social inclusion*.

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